

Response characteristics of new perchlorate selective PVC membrane electrode based on a tripodal benzimidazole derivative as a neutral carrier

Sulekh Chandra^{a*}, Inderjeet Singh^b, Praveen Kumar Tomar^{a,b}, Amrita Malik^a and Avdhesh Kumar^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Zakir Husain Delhi College (University of Delhi), J. L. Nehru Marg, New Delhi-110 002, India

E-mail : schandra_00@yahoo.com, praveen_tomar1979@yahoo.com Fax : 91-11-23215906

^bDepartment of Chemistry, C. C. R. College, Muzaffarnagar, Uttar Pradesh, India

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Abstract : The potentiometric response characteristics of a new perchlorate selective poly(vinyl chloride) membrane electrode based on a tripodal benzimidazole derivative - tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine as ionophore was investigated. The electrode exhibited a Nernstian response to perchlorate ions over the activity range of 1.5×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-1} M with a limit of detection of 5.2×10^{-8} M between pH range of 2.0–10.0, giving a relatively fast response and reversibility within 5 s. The selectivity coefficient was calculated using fixed interference method (FIM). The electrode worked well for nearly 3 months. The electrode can also be used in partially non-aqueous media having up to 25% (v/v) methanol, ethanol or acetone contents with no significant change in the value of slope or working concentration range. It was successfully applied for the direct determination of perchlorate content in water and human urine samples with satisfactory results.

Keywords : Perchlorate selective electrode, PVC membrane, potentiometry, tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine.

Introduction

Most of the analytical methods like ion chromatography¹, neutron activation analysis, atomic absorption spectrophotometry² and mass spectrometry³ etc. have been reported for the determination of ions at a very low concentration levels, but these methods require expensive instrumentation, delicate and expert handling of the sample and instrument. Hence potentiometric determination based on ion selective electrodes (ISEs) offer several advantages such as ease of preparation, low cost, simple procedure and easy instrumentation. It gives relatively fast response, wide linear range, good selectivity, high detection limit and online applications as compared to other analytical methods⁴. These methods can also be used in complexes and coloured media. Therefore, there has been progressive growth in the development and applications of potentiometric electrodes based on polymeric membrane ion selective electrodes incorporating ionophores for the detection of different cations and anions and other biologically important compounds.

Perchlorate is considered as a new persistent inor-

ganic contaminant because of its specific properties, such as high water solubility, mobility and stability⁶. Perchlorate salts are used as solid propellants for rockets, explosives, pyrotechnics, such as fireworks⁷⁻⁹, gun powder, air bag inflators, growth promoters and as thyreostatic drugs in cattle fattening¹⁰. Perchlorate salts also found in food products^{11,12}, soil¹³, milk¹⁴, fertilizers¹⁵, plants¹⁶ and in human urine¹⁷. The toxicologic mechanisms through which perchlorate exerts its effects have been reviewed in some reports^{18,19}.

Therefore, determination of perchlorate ion in various samples such as ground water, propellants, explosives and urine in the presence of other anions is a special importance²⁰. During the last three decades, many efforts have been focused on the introduction of perchlorate-selective electrodes. Most of these reported electrodes were polymeric liquid membranes based on ion exchangers, where the electroactive species including perchlorate ion-association complexes with cations and different metal chelate²¹, long chain quaternary ammonium ion²² and organic dye²³ have been dissolved in various organic sol-

vents. However, most of these electrodes are not sensitive and selective enough to permit selective measurement of low levels of perchlorate and also are susceptible to serious interferences from other common anions such as OH^- , NO_3^- , SCN^- , ClO_3^- and I^- . Only recently, a few carrier-based perchlorate-selective electrodes with improved selectivity and sensitivity were reported²⁴⁻³¹.

Due to our continuing efforts in this direction, we have fabricated a perchlorate-selective PVC based membrane, electrode using a tripod benzimidazole derivative – tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine, as a novel carrier. The performance of our proposed electrode in many respects such as wide linear range, low detection limit, less response time, Nernstian slope and long life time is better than previously reported perchlorate selective electrodes in literature.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments :

All the reagents used were of analytical grade. High molecular weight poly(vinyl chloride) (PVC), tetrahydrofuran (THF), nitrilotriacetic acid, 1,2-diaminobenzene, bromoethane, dimethyl sebacate (DMS), tri-*n*-butylphosphate (TBP), di-butylphthalate (DBF), *n*-butylacetate (NBA) and cation additive hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (HTAB) were purchased from Merck and used as received. The anionic salts of sodium or potassium were of analytical grade and used without any further purification except dried over P_4O_{10} . Solutions of anionic salts 0.1 M were prepared in doubly distilled water.

The ionophore used in the electrode preparation was synthesized in the laboratory and then characterized. The C, H, N was analyzed on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. IR spectrum (KBr) was recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR spectrum BX-II spectrophotometer. Electron impact mass spectrum was recorded on Joel-MS Route mass spectrometer. A Perkin-Elmer Model 3100 atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) with a graphite furnace was used to determine the concentration of anion in the standard solutions.

Synthesis of tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine :

1,2-Diaminobenzene (10.55 g, 0.097 mol) was ground to a fine powder and intimately mixed with nitrilotriacetic acid (1.91 g, 0.01 mol). The mixture was heated at 170–180 °C for 1 h which stage effervescence had ceased. After heating the mixture was cooled and dilute (~4 M) hydrochloric acid (~150 mL) was added, a grayish blue

precipitate out, which was washed with acetone. The precipitate was then dissolved in water and neutralized with dilute ammonia. The off-white precipitate was collected, recrystallized from acetone and ground to a fine powder prior to vacuum drying (5 g, 90%). After being thoroughly dried, this material was suspended in dry tetrahydrofuran (~50 mL) and stirred overnight with NaOH (1.4 g). Bromoethane (9 g) was added and the solution was left stirring for 2 days. The solvents were then stripped to dryness and the resulting powder dissolved in chloroform. The insoluble NaBr was removed by filtration and the filtrate was stripped to a very small volume. A little acetone was added and upon standing a white powder was deposited, which was dried in vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The chemical characterization of the synthesized compound was carried by the spectroscopic methods. The results obtained were similar to those reported earlier³² (Fig. 1). Found : C, 72.9; H, 6.3; N, 19.80. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7$: C, 73.31, H, 6.72; N, 19.95%; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 7.6–7.3 (12H, m), 4.4 (6H, s), 3.6 (2H, q), 1.0 (9H, t); MS (m/z) : 491.

Fig. 1. Structure of tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine (ionophore).

Electrode preparation :

Different membrane compositions were prepared by dissolving the ionophore, PVC, plasticizer and the cation additive in 5 mL THF (Table 1). The resulting clear solution was evaporated slowly until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (5 mm) was dipped into the mixture for ~5 s, so that a non-transparent membrane 0.3 mm thick was formed. The tube was then pulled out from the mixture and kept at room temperature for ~24 h. The tube was then filled with an internal solution (1.0×10^{-1} M KClO_4). The electrode was finally conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a 1.0×10^{-1} M KClO_4 solution.

Table 1. Optimization and different composition of membranes

Sl. no.	PVC	Plasticizer	Ionophore	Additive HTAB	Slope (mV/decade) (M)	Response time (s)	Working concentration range (M)
1.	33	-	4	8	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1}	55.4 ± 0.4	12
2.	30	61 (DMS)	4	5	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1}	56.5 ± 0.4	9
3.	33	63 (DBP)	3	1	1.5×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-1}	59.7 ± 0.2	5
4.	33	61 (DBP)	4	2	2.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-1}	58.4 ± 0.6	8
5.	32	61 (TBP)	5	2	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1}	57.5 ± 0.5	9
6.	31	61 (NBA)	5	3	1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1}	56.4 ± 0.3	7

Emf measurements :

Potentiometric study of the electrode was carried out by the following cell assembly :

Hg-Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (saturated) || internal solution 1.0×10^{-1} M KClO₄ | PVC membrane | test solution | Hg₂Cl₂-Hg, KCl (saturated).

Potential differences between the ion selective electrodes and the double junction calomel electrodes were measured with Systronics type 335 digital pH, mV meter at room temperature.

Procedure for the determination of perchlorate in water and urine samples :

Water and urine samples of different perchlorate concentrations were prepared by adding known amounts of perchlorate to blank water and urine. The pH of an appropriate volume of perchlorate sample was adjusted at 7.0 by the addition an appropriate amount of HCl or NaOH and the solution was diluted to 50 mL with dis-

tilled water. The perchlorate-selective and reference electrodes were immersed and the perchlorate concentration was determined by direct potentiometry by using the standard addition technique. A blank value for the corresponding blank water sample or urine was also obtained to correct the above results.

Results and discussion

The synthesized tripodal benzimidazole derivative - tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)methylamine was used as a neutral carrier ionophore to fabricate a new poly(vinyl chloride) perchlorate selective membrane electrode in PVC matrix. The ionophore has four coordination sites due to the presence of nitrogen as donor atoms to form the metal chelate complexes.

Working concentration range and slope :

The potential of the cell set-up with membrane of ionophore was determined as a function of ClO₄⁻ activity and the results obtained are shown in Fig. 2. Cation additive hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide (HTAB) was added

Fig. 2. Potentiometric response curve for different concentrations.

to all the prepared membranes to reduce the interference from sample cations, optimize sensing selectivity and to reduce bulk membrane impedance³³. It is seen from Fig. 1 that the electrode No. 1 having the membrane of ionophore without plasticizer exhibits linear response over a working concentration range of 1.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1} M with a slope of 55.4 mV/decade of activity. The slope of the membrane is near-Nernstian and the working concentration range is narrow. The improvement in the performance was attempted by the addition of plasticizers to the membranes. The addition of plasticizers not only improves the workability of the membranes, but also contributes significantly towards the improvement in the working concentration range, stability and shelf life of the electrode^{34,35}. However, the selectivity remains usually unaffected and mainly depends on the metal-ionophore interaction. The plasticizer to be used in membranes should exhibit high lipophilicity, high molecular weight, low tendency for exudation from the polymer matrix, low vapour pressure and high capacity to dissolve the substrate and other additives present in the membrane. Additionally, its viscosity and dielectric constant should be adequate³⁶. Thus, four plasticizers namely, DMS, TBP, DBP and NBA were added in an attempt to improve the performance of the electrode. All performance characteristics of the electrodes are compiled in Table 1. It is seen that the addition of four plasticizers added, DBP improves performance of the electrode (No. 3) as it exhibits the maximum working concentration range of 1.5×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-1} M with an almost Nernstian slope of 59.7 mV/decade of activity. Thus, the mem-

branes even without a plasticizer perform well and the addition of plasticizers DMS, TBP and NBA shows less improvement in the performance. Only DBP plasticizer improves the performance. The lower detection limit achieved for the electrode is 5.2×10^{-8} M evaluated on the basis of IUPAC recommendation³⁷. Repeated monitoring of potentials (15 measurements) at the same concentration (1.0×10^{-3} M) gave a standard deviation of ± 0.2 mV. The performance of the membrane without ionophore (dummy membrane) was also investigated and no potential was generated.

Effect of internal reference solution :

The influence of the concentration of internal solution on the potential response of the polymeric electrode for ClO_4^- was studied. The concentration was varied from 1.0×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-5} M and the potential response of the electrode was observed. It was found that the best results in terms of slope and working concentration range has been obtained with internal solution of activity 1.0×10^{-1} M concentration of KClO_4 . KClO_4 solution was quite appropriate for the smooth functioning of the proposed electrode.

pH and non-aqueous effect :

The influence of pH of the test solution on the potential response of the membrane electrode was tested in the pH range of 1.0–11.0 at two different concentration, 1.0×10^{-2} and 1.0×10^{-3} M. The pH was adjusted by adding HCl or NaOH solution and the results are illustrated in Fig. 3. It has been observed that the response of the electrode is independent of pH in wide range of 2.0–10.0 and beyond, which the potential changes considerably.

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on the potential response at two different concentrations.

The performance of the electrode was further assessed in partially non-aqueous media, i.e. methanol-water, ethanol-water, acetone-water mixtures. It was concluded that the membrane electrodes worked satisfactorily in solutions having a maximum of 25% (v/v) non-aqueous content. In these mixtures the working concentration range and slope remained unaffected. Therefore, the electrode works well in the presence of up to 25% non-aqueous content. However, above 25% non-aqueous content, the decrease in concentration range is significant.

Response and life time of electrode :

Dynamic response time is an important factor for a perchlorate sensitive electrode. In the present study, the practical response time was recorded by changing solution with different high-to-low ClO_4^- concentrations. It was observed that the electrode reaches the equilibrium response in a very short time (approx. 5 s).

The lifetime of the electrode having DBP plasticizer was determined by recording its potentials at an optimum pH value and by plotting its calibration curves for each day. It was observed that there was no significant change in the slope and working range of the electrode for a period of 3 months. After 3 months a slight gradual decreases in the slopes (from 59.7 ± 0.2 to 53.6 ± 0.5 mV per decade) was observed. During this period, the electrodes were used over extended period of time (one hour per day). However, it is important to emphasize that the membranes were stored in a $1.0 \times 10^{-2} M \text{ClO}_4^-$ solution when not in use.

Potentiometric selectivity :

Selectivity is one of the most important characteristic of an electrode. Study of selectivity behavior helps to ascertain the preferential response of anion selective electrode towards primary analyte ion in the presence of secondary ions. Selectivity of anion selective electrode is measured in terms of selectivity coefficient $K_{A,B}^{\text{pot}}$. In the present study, selectivity coefficients, for the proposed perchlorate selective polymeric membrane electrode were calculated using fixed interference method (FIM) as suggested by sa'ez de Viteri and Diamond³⁸. In the present study, the potential was measured for solutions containing varying concentration of ClO_4^- and fixed interfering ion concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-2} M$). The selectivity coefficient values so observed by this method are presented in

Table 2. As it is seen, the electrode exhibits selective response toward ClO_4^- ion and follows a selectivity pattern for several anions in the order : $\text{ClO}_4^- > \text{SCN}^- > \text{PO}_4^{3-} > \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-} > \text{CH}_3\text{COO}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{NO}_3^- > \text{I}^- > \text{SO}_4^{2-} > \text{Br}^-$. It is interesting to note that the observed selectivity pattern for the proposed electrode significantly differs from the so-called Hofmeister selectivity sequence (i.e. selectivity based solely on the lipophilicity of anions)³⁹. A value of selectivity coefficient equal to 1.0 would indicate that the membrane responds equally to primary as well as interfering ion. A value smaller than 1.0 indicates that it responds more to primary ion than interfering ion and in such a case, the electrode is said to be selective to primary ion over interfering ion. It is seen from the Table 2 that the selectivity coefficients are in the order of 10^{-2} or lower for almost all diverse ions tested. Thus, these ions would not cause any significant interference, in the estimation of ClO_4^- ions by this electrode unless present in large amounts. The electroactive material of the membrane is ionophore and thus allows the transport of ions only, hence the membrane responds to ions only. The membrane would not allow organic substances to transport, hence they should not cause any interference.

Table 2. Selectivity coefficient $K_{A,B}^{\text{pot}}$ values of perchlorate-selective electrode by FIM

Interfering ion	Selectivity coefficients
CH_3COO^-	3.7×10^{-2}
I^-	2.8×10^{-3}
PO_4^{3-}	4.6×10^{-3}
Cl^-	3.3×10^{-3}
SO_4^{2-}	2.2×10^{-4}
Br^-	2.1×10^{-3}
NO_3^-	3.2×10^{-4}
SCN^-	5.2×10^{-3}
$\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$	3.9×10^{-3}

Analytical applications :

Quantitative measurements of perchlorate ions in water and urine samples were found to be important because of health effect of perchlorate ion in human being⁴⁰. Thus, to assess the practical application of proposed perchlorate-selective electrode, the proposed PVC membrane was used in the recovery of perchlorate ions from blank water and urine samples. Different amounts (15, 25, 40 and 20, 30,

40) ppm of NaClO_4 was spiked into water and human urine samples and then the ClO_4^- contents of the samples were measured and the results of the analysis of the samples are given in Table 3. Good recoveries were obtained in all samples.

Table 3. Determination of perchlorate ions in drinking water and human urine samples

Sample	Added (ppm)	Found by proposed electrode (ppm)	Found by AAS (ppm)	Recovery (%)
Water	15	14.89	14.91	99.2
	25	24.64	24.67	98.5
	40	39.46	39.49	98.6
Human urine	20	19.75	19.79	98.7
	30	29.69	29.74	98.9
	40	39.54	39.54	98.8

Conclusions :

The present work reveals that the proposed perchlorate selective PVC membrane electrode based on a synthesized tripodal benzimidazole derivative - tris[2-(1-ethylbenzimidazolyl)]methylamine as an ionophore displays good sensitivity and selectivity for perchlorate ions in terms of Nernstian slope (59.7 ± 0.2 mV/decade), lower detection limit (5.2×10^{-8} M), and wide concentration range (1.5×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-1} M). To the best of our knowledge, the proposed electrode is the better PVC membrane electrode than reported earlier^{24,25,27,28,31}. The proposed electrode is easy to prepare, has fast response time and permits the estimation of perchlorate ion content in synthetic water and urine samples without the need for preconcentration or pretreatment steps and without significant interaction from other anionic species present in the samples.

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